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Data management plan (DMP)

NBA MVP Likelihood Investigator

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	24/11/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project
1.5	25/11/2025	Updated DMP, additional information added
2.0	28/11/2025	Experiment data and repository is uploaded
3.0	29/11/2025	Finalised DMP after FAIR self-assessment plan

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Project details

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
CSV	Comma Separated Values
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
...	...
...	...
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...	...

Content

INTRODUCTION	4
Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data	4
Relevant Policies and Guidelines	4
1. DATA DESCRIPTION	5
1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced	5
1b Data generation and reuse	5
2. DOCUMENTATION AND DATA QUALITY	6
2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation	6
2b Data quality control	6
3. STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING RESEARCH PROCESS	6
3a Storage and backup facilities	6
3b Data security and protection of sensitive data	6
4. LEGAL AND ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS	7
4a Personal data	7
4b Intellectual property rights and ownership	7
4c Ethical issues	7
5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION	7
5a Data publication and access conditions	7
5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data	8
6. RDM RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES	8
6a RDM-roles and responsibilities	8
6b Resources	8

Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Historical NBA Data and Player Box Scores Cleaned	Structured text	.csv	< 500 MB	no

Description for "Historical NBA Data and Player Box Scores Cleaned":

The first dataset is the cleaned version of the Historical NBA Data and Player Box Scores dataset from Kaggle.

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Historical NBA Data and Player Box Scores	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/eoinamoore/historical-nba-data-and-player-box-scores/data	MIT License	no

Description for "Historical NBA Data and Player Box Scores" (R1):

This dataset contains player and team box scores and statistics for NBA games from 1947 up to and including the 2025–2026 season. It is updated regularly and provides a comprehensive basis for exploring player performance and team dynamics. In this project, only the parts relevant to the 2025–2026 regular season are used. No additional external dataset (R2) is used in the current project version.

Note – As mentioned in the project description initially a second dataset was planned for reuse. R2 would have been a dataset accumulated from the NBA Statistics platform to update the initial dataset R1, however in the meantime the authors of R1 decided to update this dataset for the current season, therefore this R2 dataset is currently not needed.

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The research data are processed using Python and standard data-science libraries (pandas, numpy, matplotlib, scikit-learn). The main workflows are implemented in Jupyter notebooks and Python scripts contained in the GitHub repository and in the ZIP archive uploaded to TU Wien Research Data. Reused data from R1 (Historical NBA Data and Player Box Scores) are downloaded from Kaggle and stored locally under `data/raw/`. The cleaned dataset P1 is generated by a documented preprocessing pipeline (`src/groundwork/preprocessing.ipynb`), which selects relevant columns and exports the result as a CSV file under `data/processed/`.

All steps are scripted and reproducible; no manual row-by-row editing is performed.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The whole project (code, documentation and exemplary processed dataset) is kept in a public GitHub repository. Versioning of scripts, notebooks and small configuration files is handled via Git. Within the project, raw and processed data are clearly separated in different folders (e.g. data/raw/ and data/processed/) and each level is accompanied by explanatory documentation.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide documentation at three levels:

- a project-level README describing the overall goals, folder structure, software requirements and workflow;
- a dataset-level description for P1 (Cleaned NBA Player Game Statistics 2025–2026), including variable definitions, provenance and preprocessing steps;
- a short README in data/raw/ explaining where the original external datasets (R1) can be downloaded and under which conditions they may be used.

This documentation helps others to identify, understand and reuse the data and code. P1 is uploaded together with the rest of the software and folders to the institutional research data platform, and a descriptive record (title, description, keywords, licence information) has been provided there.

Where appropriate, we use consistent naming conventions and, as far as possible, controlled vocabularies (e.g. standard team names, season identifiers) to support interoperability and machine-actionability. A structured README-based documentation approach is used throughout the project to facilitate future data reuse.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: repeated samples or measurements and data entry validation. Verification that key identifier are present and not empty. Basic range checks for core statistics. Reproducibility checks to make sure the notebooks present can be run and the output can be obtained automatically.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data are ensured by Peter Reti (responsible for data management and the DMP). Working copies of code and small datasets are stored in a version-controlled Git repository (GitHub), which is mirrored locally.

The cleaned dataset P1 and the accompanying project files are archived in TU Wien Research Data as a ZIP package for publication and long-term preservation. Raw data from R1 are obtained directly from the external source (Kaggle) and are not redistributed; they can be redownloaded as needed by following the instructions in data/raw/README.md.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any

sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	reading only
R1	writing	reading only	no access

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: The control access over all datasets in this project will be decided solely by the Project Leader.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data	DOI:10.70124/vmf7g-nv342	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data.

This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: There are no specific softwares or technologies required as the final data will be available in a csv format.

This Data Management Plan File is stored in Zenodo, separately from the dataset and source code.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Sport enthusiasts, especially people who are interested in basketball. NBA analysts and scouts along with aspiring data scientists as the data is great for further research.

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The Project Leader, Peter Reti will direct the data management process overall and is responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.